

PROGRESSIVE FAILURE ANALYSIS OF FILAMENT WOUND COMPOSITE TUBES UNDER INTERNAL PRESSURE

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ABSTRACT

Complete understanding of the multiple complex failure mechanisms of high performance tubular composite structures is mandatory to enable implementation of more reliable failure and damage models to predict their mechanical behavior. These structures present non-linear behavior because their failure occurs by means of a progressive series of events, and their catastrophic failure rarely occurs at the first-ply failure load. This study aims at presenting a damage model based on progressive failure analysis to evaluate the mechanical response of composite tubes subjected to hydrostatic internal pressure load. Composite tubes wound at $\pm 55^\circ$ have the highest burst pressure and radial deformation resistances, and the addition of a hoop layer harmed the mechanical performance of the tube. All tubes tested failed in the matrix by tensile transverse stresses and in-plane shear, once the shear stresses increase up to winding angle of $\pm 55^\circ$, decreasing for higher angles, where transverse stresses dominate the failure mode.

1 INTRODUCTION

The usage of composite materials in structural applications have been largely increased over the last years, mainly due to their high stiffness- and strength-to-weight ratio, besides their corrosion resistance. Among others, marine, aerospace and aeronautic sectors are continuously replacing metallic structural parts by composites, due to their limitation of payload. Nevertheless, the use of composites in structural counterparts is limited due to their complex failure mechanisms and unknown damage parameters.

There are several criteria to predict failure in composite materials, since the most disseminated were developed by Tsai and Wu [1], Azzi and Tsai [2], Hashin [3] and Puck [4]. As can be noted by analyzing these criteria, the material fails when the first ply reaches the limit failure index throughout the laminate. There are numerous events that occur before and after the failure in an orthotropic material, so a progressive failure analysis (PFA), which is developed to account for the continuous stiffness degradation and load-bearing ability of composite structure, must be taken into account, as well as the damage initiation and evolution.

Damage mechanics is useful to correlate the mathematical science with quantitative descriptions of physical events, which change the material's behavior when subjected to a particular loading [5], where this major aim is to describe the material response after damaged. The greatest challenge in developing a computational modelling with an efficient procedure is to predict the damage growth along the total step time and how to relate micro-structural changes with the material response.

Failure process of a composite laminate involves numerous failure mechanisms, such as fiber fracture, fiber/matrix debonding, fiber kinking, fiber pullout, interface cracking, matrix cracking, and delamination [6]. A unidirectional polymer composite laminate presents two types of failure modes: intra-ply and inter-ply failure modes. An intra-ply failure mode comprises damage in fibers, matrix and/or fiber/matrix, whereas inter-ply failures are limited to delaminations.

Although these failure modes are hard to predict, cylindrical composite structures have even more complex failure modes, especially when under biaxial loadings, such as internal and external hydrostatic pressure. The damage initiation and evolution are crucial to predict reliable stiffness degradation, being the main key to predict the load-bearing ability of composite tubes under complex loadings [7]. Liu et al. [8] made a review about numerical methods and optimal designs for composite pressure vessels, dealing with PFA and damage evolution. There are various researches emphasizing failure in wound cylindrical composites, however studies accounting for damaging evolution, progressive failure and different failure modes have not been deeply studied.

On this context, this paper deals with the development of a finite element model for filament wound composite tubes subjected to internal pressure loading. A damage model based on progressive failure analysis was developed and implemented as a User Material Subroutine (UMAT), written in Fortran language and linked to Abaqus™ software platform.

2 MATERIAL MODEL

Ribeiro et al. [7] developed the material model with a mathematical formulation at a mesoscale approach, where that model was adapted to the material and geometry herein used. The model regards to the composite lamina under plane stress state and the damage is considered uniform throughout the laminate thickness [9].

2.1 Fiber modelling

A unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite laminate under tensile loading in the fiber direction (σ_{11}) is linear elastic with brittle fracture. The model assumes that the fiber behavior is not influenced by damage state in the matrix. Thus, for tensile load in fiber direction, the maximum stress criterion is used to identify the fiber failure:

$$\frac{\sigma_{11}}{X_t} \leq 1 \quad (1)$$

After failure is reached, the damage variable in fiber direction (d_1) is set to be "1". There is no evolution of d_1 aiming at representing the catastrophic failure of the carbon fiber. To avoid possible localization issues, the degradation of properties is calculated in the step " i ", however it is applied into the step " $i + 1$ ", thus improving the convergence process. Therefore, although this strategy can improve the convergence process, it is required to control the step time in order to limit the element size between the last step (calculation of the damage) and next step (application of the damage). Thus, a parametric step-size sensitivity analysis in the finite element model should be carried out to find best results.

The fiber behavior under compressive longitudinal load is set to be linear elastic until a specified value, after that, a non-linear elastic behavior is observed. The linear elastic to non-linear elastic limit (X_{C0}) is then used in Eq. 2 to represent the compressive failure, as follows:

$$\frac{|\sigma_{11}|}{X_{C0}} \leq 1 \quad (2)$$

After $|\sigma_{11}| \geq X_{C0}$ any increase in the compression loads in fiber direction results in a non-linear elastic stress-strain behavior. This non-linear elastic behavior is simulated using a secant modulus as

can be seen in Eq. 3:

$$E_{11} = \frac{X_{c0}}{|\varepsilon_{11}|} (1 - h(\varepsilon_{11})) + h(\varepsilon_{11})E_{11_0} \quad (3)$$

Where $h(\varepsilon_{11})$ is obtained from the fit of stress-strain plots for 0° specimens under compressive loading, ε_{11} is the strain in longitudinal direction and E_{11_0} is the initial elastic modulus from 0° specimens under compression loading.

2.2 Matrix modelling

In a unidirectional quasi-flat filament wound laminate, the damage process in the matrix is essentially dominated by the transverse loading (σ_{22}) and shear loading (τ_{12}). A non-linear behavior in the matrix is reported due to inelastic strains and damage in matrix [10]. To model the damage process in matrix, two internal damage variables, d_2 (related to σ_{22}) and d_6 (related to τ_{12}), were used. Based on Continuous Damage Mechanics, the hypothesis of effective stress links the damage variables to the stresses [9], and Eq. 4 gives this relationship:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \hat{\sigma}_{11} \\ \hat{\sigma}_{22} \\ \hat{\tau}_{12} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1/1 - d_1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1/1 - d_2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1/1 - d_6 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{11} \\ \sigma_{22} \\ \tau_{12} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Since $\hat{\sigma}_{ij}$ $\hat{\tau}_{ij}$ are the second order effective stress tensors.

According to Herakovich [9], the damage strain energy density can be described in function of effective stresses considering only for matrix phase stresses, as shows Eq. (5):

$$E_D = \frac{1}{2} \left[\frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_+}{E_{22_0}(1-d_2)} + \frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_-}{E_{22_0}} + \frac{|\tau_{12}^2|}{G_{12_0}(1-d_6)} \right] \quad (5)$$

Where $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_+ = \sigma_{22}^2$ if $\sigma_{22} > 0$, otherwise $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_+ = 0$ if $\sigma_{22} < 0$. Similarly, $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_- = -\sigma_{22}^2$ if $\sigma_{22} < 0$, otherwise $\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_- = 0$ if $\sigma_{22} > 0$. Ladeveze and LeDantec [11] introduced two thermodynamic forces into their model, which relates the damage variables with the strain energy density (E_D), described in Eq. 5 and Eq. 6:

$$Y_2 = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d_2} = \frac{\langle \sigma_{22}^2 \rangle_+}{2E_{22_0}(1-d_2)^2} \quad (6)$$

$$Y_6 = \frac{\partial E_D}{\partial d_6} = \frac{\langle \tau_{12}^2 \rangle_+}{2G_{12_0}(1-d_6)^2} \quad (7)$$

The damage initiation in a composite can be identified after the deterioration of materials properties. This deterioration can be assessed by carrying out cyclic tests. The model regards that the damage process starts when the stress \times strain curve are no longer linear.

Another aspect of the present model must be highlighted, which consists in an adjustment of the Poisson's coefficient for consider the damage effect. Using CDM formulation performed by Matzenmiller et al. [12], Eq. 8 gives the compliance tensor:

$$D = \frac{1}{K} \begin{bmatrix} (1-d_1)E_{11} & (1-d_1)(1-d_2)\nu_{21}E_{22} & 0 \\ (1-d_1)(1-d_2)\nu_{12}E_{11} & (1-d_2)E_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & K(1-d_6)G_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Since, $K = (1 - (1 - d_1)(1 - d_2)\nu_{12}\nu_{21})$. Aiming at avoid the material self-healing, the damage parameters (d_1 , d_2 e d_6) are assumed as the maximum "0.99" along the simulation [7].

3 FINITE ELEMENT STRUCTURAL MODELLING

The structural modelling was performed based on finite element method (FEM) and was conducted with Abaqus™ 6.14 commercial software platform. Non-linear geometry was considered in all cases

since large and unbalanced deformations were foreseen.

The composite tubes were modelled by using four node reduced integration shell element (S4R) with hourglass control. The reduced integration element was chosen in order to reduce the simulation time and to avoid numerical issues. The comprehensive material properties of the carbon/epoxy laminates were experimentally measured [13] and they are presented in Table 1. The composite layers were modelled as conventional shell with Simpson thickness integration rule and three integrations points in each layer.

Elastic constants	E_1 (GPa)	129.3
	$E_2 = E_3$ (GPa)	9.11
	$\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$	0.32
	ν_{23}	0.35
	$G_{12} = G_{13}$ (GPa)	5.44
	G_{23} (GPa)	2.10
Strengths	X_t (MPa)	1409.9
	X_c (MPa)	-740.0
	Y_t (MPa)	42.5
	Y_c (MPa)	-140.3
	S_{12} (MPa)	68.9

Table 1: Material properties used as input in the numerical models.

The tubes were realistically modelled as is in filament winding process, taking into account i) symmetry in the layers, ii) thickness built-up at the turnaround zones, and iii) winding angle variation at the turnaround zones. The input data of the tubes were performed by using the dedicated software for filament winding process CADWind 2007, and that data was used as basis for the mesh generation in Abaqus™ software. Figure 1 shows typical peculiarities of the developed models and geometry.

Figure 1: Laminate thickness (a), winding angle (b) and winding angle deviation (c) of the tubes.

Two groups of tubes were studied: *i*) with variable winding angle, $[\pm 35]_5$, $[\pm 45]_5$, $[\pm 55]_5$, $[\pm 65]_5$, $[\pm 75]_5$ and $[90]_5$; and *ii*) with a hoop layer added at different positions into the laminates wound at $\pm 55^\circ$, namely: $[90/\pm 55_4]$, $[\pm 55_2/90/\pm 55_2]$, $[\pm 55_4/90]$ and $[90/\pm 55_3/90]$. The study of the second group of tubes is motivated based on the efficiency of the hoop layer, since several works [14,15] just use this layer at the innermost and/or outermost layers, once the innermost helps in a better adhesion of non-geodesic layers onto the mandrel, avoiding slipping during winding, whereas the outermost one is effective for a better compaction of the laminate. Thus, the parametric study of the second group is to evaluate until where a hoop layer may have a structural responsibility in the tube under internal pressure loading.

Figure 2 depicts the typical mesh used for all simulation herein developed with the shell element highlighted, which is used for the models. This mesh was chosen after a preliminary mesh sensitivity analysis, since this mesh density has a good balance between computational cost and accuracy on the results, since it does not present significant differences on the results.

Figure 2: Details of the finite element model.

In order to represent the internal pressure test as boundary condition, axial displacement of both flange areas were restricted. A hydrostatic pressure load of 20 MPa (200 bar) was applied into the internal wall of the tube, as shows Figure 3. The cylinders has $l = 381$ mm and $\Phi = 136$ mm.

Figure 3: Typical loads and boundary conditions.

4 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Linear-elastic analysis

In the present work a damage model based on PFA is proposed for evaluate composite tubes subjected to internal pressure loading. Aiming at understand the mechanical response of the cylinders and test the mesh density efficiency, a linear-elastic analysis is carried out and four failure criteria based on first-ply failure principle was applied. Figure 4 presents the burst pressure for the tubes with different winding sequence.

As shows Figure 4, the burst pressure increases until the winding sequence of $[\pm 55]_5$ laminates, where an abrupt drop is noticed after this stacking sequence, for all analyzed failure criteria. Among

the criterion used, two of them are associated with failure modes, namely Maximum Stress and Hashin. Both Max. Stress and Hashin pointed matrix failure in tensile.

Figure 4: Burst pressure for tubes with different winding angles.

A winding angle of around 55° is considered as being optimum for filament wound composite tubes for this loading case. The conventional derivation is based on netting analysis and it applies only to cylinders internally pressurized, where the hoop/axial stresses ratio of (σ_h/σ_a) is 2 [16]. Netting analysis neglects the contribution of the matrix to the structure and considers only the stress in fiber direction (σ_f). For a given winding angle, hoop and axial stresses are defined as:

$$\sigma_h = \sigma_f \cdot \sin^2 \varphi \quad (9)$$

$$\sigma_a = \sigma_f \cdot \cos^2 \varphi \quad (10)$$

If $\sigma_h/\sigma_a = 2$, thus rearranging the system, a $\varphi = 54.7^\circ$ is found. By considering the volume of a geodesic wound cylinder, this optimum winding angle maximizes its overall volume, which leads to a proportional increase in length and radius of the cylinder [16].

4.2 Models with damage

4.2.1 Step-size sensibility

In Section 3 of this work, the material model was detailed demonstrated. Moreover, it is valid to mention that after failure is reached into the simulation, the damage is calculated in the subsequent step increment. This means that the simulation may be strongly dependent of the step-size, since between two increments too much information can be lost. In this way, a preliminary step-size sensibility (Figure 5) seems plausible to achieve accurate solutions. As expected, the burst pressure is highly dependent of the maximum increment size, where, for instance, $[\pm 35]_5$ points a burst pressure of 77.64 bar for a maximum increment of 1.0, whereas for a maximum increment of 0.1 the burst pressure is of 91.70 bar. This situation is a clear evidence of the step-time dependence of this material model, once step-size of 1.0 was more accurate than 0.1, because in the model with maximum step-size of 0.1 an increment was completed just before failure occurs, thus making this model very inaccurate. For a step-size of 0.05, the decrease in pressure was of $\approx 20\%$, but after this step-size the fluctuation in the values was not significant, which means that this step-size is suitable for the analysis. A more refined model could be carried out, but the computational cost increases highly, making the simulation too time-consuming.

Figure 5: Step-size sensibility for the model $[\pm 35]_5$ with damage.

4.2.2 Parametric study

Figure 6 presents the internal pressure strength of the group 1 of tubes, by varying the winding angle with non-geodesic layers. These models with damage presented the same trend in burst pressure for the cylinder analyzed, however all of them point an increase in the maximum pressure supported when compared to burst pressures calculated with first-ply failure criteria. All specimens presented similar failure mode, since they failed by matrix tensile but also damaged by shear. Comparing the failure mode of the tubes herein presented with Hashin [17] failure criteria, both transverse stresses and in-plane shear stress components contribute to matrix cracking. It means that increasing the winding angle from 55° upwards, the in-plane shear stress decreases and the tensile and/or compressive transverse stress increases. Thus, monotonic laminates with winding angles higher than $\pm 55^\circ$ the tensile transverse stress becomes dominant when compared to in-plane shear [15]. Otherwise, for winding sequence lower than $\pm 55^\circ$, in-plane shear stress is more influential than transverse stresses.

Figure 6: Bust pressure for tubes with different monotonic laminates.

By modelling damage in a composite laminate, the structure does not fail when the first ply fails, but rather only when the last ply that contributes to the remaining strength of the structure reaches a maximum failure index. This is the main reason that PFA is mandatory to know the events occurring

into the laminate after an “n” ply not support a given load. Martins et al. [18] performed a PFA based on a strain-continuum damage formulation for glass/epoxy filament wound composite tubes subjected to hydrostatic internal pressure, and they also found the 55° winding angle as optimum and with matrix-dominating failure. The results in Figure 6 are also in accordance with the study performed by Raffie and Reshadi [15], where they evaluated the effect of winding angle on the mechanical behavior of composite tubes under internal pressure, and no fiber failure was reported in any layer.

Table 2 shows some properties of the tube just when the structure fails. The damage started to act at different proportionally level loads for the winding sequence analyzed, where the specimen $[\pm 35]_5$ started damaging at 63.18 bar and failed at 76.16 and the failure started at the outermost layer on both + and - Φ cross ply with high influence of shear. The cylinders $[\pm 45]_5$ began to damage mainly by transverse tensile in 71% of the burst pressure, since this fail is influenced by scissoring, transverse tensile and in-plane shear (winding sequence in which this component is more decisive).

<i>Specimen</i>	<i>First failed ply</i>	<i>Starting damage at matrix (bar)</i>	σ_{11} (MPa)	σ_{22} (MPa)	$l\varepsilon_{11}$ (%)	$l\varepsilon_{22}$ (%)
$[\pm 35]_5$	5 (full)	63.18	372.78	65.86	0.279	0.686
$[\pm 45]_5$	1 (at -45°)	94.68	548.53	65.12	0.412	0.607
$[\pm 55]_5$	1 (at -55°)	129.80	690.01	65.44	0.516	0.557
$[\pm 65]_5$	1 (at -65°)	81.20	296.52	65.31	0.214	0.669
$[\pm 75]_5$	1 (at -75°)	56.24	171.53	65.26	0.117	0.695
$[\pm 90]_5$	5 (at +89.7°)	46.98	114.37	60.42	0.08	0.699

Table 2: Damage, stresses and logarithm strains at failure for tubes with different winding sequence.

Figure 7 presents burst pressure values for tubes with a hoop layers added into the laminate at different positions in the $[\pm 55]_4$ laminate. The lowest burst pressure was found for the specimen $[90/\pm 55_3/90]$, clearly affected by the replacement of two non-geodesic layers by two hoop ones, harming the structural response of the cylinder. Analyzing together the results from Figure 7 and Table 3, it can be stated that a hoop layer wound as innermost lamina turns the tube into a less rigid structure in radial direction.

Figure 7: Bust pressure for the tubes with hoop layers.

In this group with hoop layers, the specimen $[\pm 55_2/90/\pm 55_2]$ has the best behavior, once the non-geodesic layers at the innermost and outermost laminas maximize the deformation of the tube in the

circumferential direction and decrease the transverse stress in the tube. In all specimens, the failed at the hoop layer by matrix cracking and shear modes.

<i>Specimen</i>	<i>First failed ply</i>	<i>Starting damage at matrix (bar)</i>	σ_{11} (MPa)	σ_{22} (MPa)	$l\varepsilon_{11}$ (%)	$l\varepsilon_{22}$ (%)
[90/±55 ₄]	1 (at -89.7°)	104.84	412.18	65.38	0.307	0.692
[±55 ₂ /90/±55 ₂]	3 (at -89.7°)	117.18	487.33	65.05	0.363	0.685
[±55 ₄ /90]	5 (at +89.7°)	114.5	475.28	63.08	0.355	0.642
[90/±55 ₃ /90]	1 (at -89.7°)	90.94	389.37	65.52	0.290	0.700

Table 3: Burst pressure, damage properties, stresses and logarithm strains at failure for tubes with a hoop layer in the laminate.

Another issue associated with the use of cylinder specimens under hydrostatic pressure is the changes in dimensions during testing, as can be seen in Figure 8. Bulging usually occurs and it is expressed by hoop expansion of the middle section of the tube in relation to the end-reinforced sections, which are the thickest regions due to thickness built-up at the turnaround zones. It leads to a modification of the initial geometry, in particular the diameter. According to Kaddour et al. [19], bulging of the tube in internal pressure tests might create an axial tension stress acting throughout the tube wall thickness, just as found in the results herein shown.

Figure 8: Matrix failure by transverse stress (a) and shear (b) just after burst pressure for the specimen [±55₂/90/±55₂].

5 CONCLUSIONS

The scope of this study is to propose a reliable damage modelling approach based on progressive failure analysis to analyze the mechanical response of filament wound composite tubes subjected to hydrostatic internal pressure load. Representative finite element models were developed, in which the composite tube was modelled considering the thickness built-up and winding angle variation at the turnaround zones. In addition, a parametric study was performed aiming at evaluating the effects of winding sequence on the burst pressure.

The tube [±55]₅ has the best performance among all winding angles simulated. All failure modes are by matrix tensile and shear stress, since the in-plane shear efforts have a maximum for the angle of ±55° and for sequences with higher winding angle the transverse tensile stresses dominates the failure behavior. The insertion of a hoop layer replacing a non-geodesic (angle-ply) one decreased the burst pressure strength, however increased the radial stiffness (less displacement) of the tube.

The next step of this research is to carry out the hydrostatic internal pressure tests to validate the both material model with damage and finite element model with realistic modelling of the thickness

built-up and varying winding angle.

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